

Evaluation of detrimental effect on the ductility caused by the inhomogeneous skin and casting defects in a high pressure die cast recycled secondary alloy

Biswajit Dalai^a, Simon Jonsson^a, Manel da Silva^b, Fredrik Forsberg^c, Liang Yu^d, Jörgen Kajberg^{a,*}

^a Division of Solid Mechanics, Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics, Luleå University of Technology, 97187 Luleå, Sweden

^b Eurecat, Centre Tecnològic de Catalunya, Unit of Metallic and Ceramic Materials, 08290 Cerdanyola del Valles, Spain

^c Division of Fluid and Experimental Mechanics, Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics, Luleå University of Technology, 97187 Luleå, Sweden

^d Chemical Technology, Department of Civil, Environmental and Natural Resources Engineering, Luleå University of Technology, 97187 Luleå, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Secondary alloy
AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy
High pressure die casting
Ductility
Inhomogeneous skin
Porosity
Cold flake

ABSTRACT

The usage of recycled alloys in the high pressure die casting (HPDC) applications for automobiles is gaining rapid interest. Even though the skin microstructure, which is typically induced on the casting surface during the HPDC process, is believed to improve the properties of the HPDC castings, it may not always form continuously throughout on the casting surface, and thereby can influence the mechanical properties. Thus, the current study evaluated and compared the effects of inhomogeneously formed surface skin with that of other defects on the ductility exhibited by the HPDC castings of a recycled secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy. The formation of inhomogeneous skin in the current study was attributed to a phenomenon related to the “waves and lakes” type of defects created by the HPDC process. Such skin structure limited the ductility of the HPDC castings, irrespective of the tested strain rates in the current case, by undergoing abrupt fracture due to its poor bonding with the adjoining matrix resulting from the aforementioned inhomogeneity. Even if the investigated AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy contained an abundance of porosity, cold flakes and intermetallics, which are usually considered the driving factors behind the fracture of HPDC processed alloys, the effect from the inhomogeneous skin layer dominated all other factors in the current case. The order of detrimental effect on the ductility of HPDC processed AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy followed a sequence of inhomogeneous skin, cold flakes and pores, with the inhomogeneity in skin turning out to be the most harmful one.

1. Introduction

The age-old focus of the automotive industries can broadly be categorized into two aspects; cost effectiveness and safety of the passengers. When it comes to being cost effective, there has been a gradual shift towards the usage of high pressure die casting (HPDC) for producing the structural parts of automobiles. HPDC is a process with high geometrical accuracy and reduced cycle time. It allows the production of extremely thin-walled castings of large dimensions, thus largely reducing the number of parts required to produce a chassis and body-in-white (BIW) structure of an automobile. As far as the passengers' safety is concerned, the quest for an appropriate material to be used in the HPDC processed high ductility castings has evolved through the requirements of excellent

casting abilities [1,2], prevention of die sticking tendency to improve the surface finish [3,4] and avoidance of brittle β -Al₅FeSi intermetallic formation which is known for restricting the ductility of the parts [5–7], subsequently leading to the development of primary AlSi10MnMg alloy. The said primary alloy is emergingly used in the structural components of automobiles, such as, in the A, B, C pillars, shock towers, longitudinal carriers, transverse bearing beams, etc. The chemical composition recommended for the primary alloys with Fe content maximum up to 0.25 wt% and Mn content within 0.4–0.8 wt% (according to EN AC – 43500 standard [8]) suppresses the formation of deleterious β -Al₅FeSi compounds (henceforth denoted as “ β -Fe”) by forming less harmful Fe based α -intermetallic compounds (henceforth denoted as “ α -Fe”) [6,7,9], thereby improving their mechanical properties as compared to the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: jorgen.kajberg@ltu.se (J. Kajberg).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2025.114775>

Received 2 October 2024; Received in revised form 7 January 2025; Accepted 26 January 2025

Available online 27 January 2025

1044-5803/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Inc. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

conventional Al-Si-Mg based alloys with high Fe content. However, restricting the Fe content in the alloy to the desired amount increases the production cost [5].

In the recent times, a third aspect has been added to the focus of the automotive industries, which is to use sustainable materials that are more environment friendly with respect to industrial applications. Therefore, there is a growing interest for producing materials that are recycled from scrap [10], thus promoting sustainability, and at the same time can be used as a substitution of primary AlSi10MnMg alloy. Such recycled materials, also regarded as secondary alloys, usually contain higher Fe content than their primary counterparts due to the gradual accumulation of Fe during repeated scrap recycling [4,7] (and will therefore be denoted as AlSi10MnMg(Fe) henceforth). The usage of such secondary alloys should not only reduce the production cost and the CO₂ emission but also be able to exhibit mechanical properties within a range that are desirable in the cast components [11–13]. However, due to their higher Fe content than the recommended limit, these alloys pose a risk of forming the β -Fe compounds in their microstructure which could be a limiting factor in the application of high ductility HPDC castings. Thus, the research on secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloys with optimized chemical composition that can be able to exhibit mechanical properties within the range reported for their primary counterpart has gained attention in the present-day.

The attempts made to optimize the AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy composition manifests that, in order to replace the β -Fe compounds with their α -Fe counterparts, the optimum level of Mn:Fe ratio lies within 0.58 and 1.3 based on the Fe content in the alloy [11,14–17]. The size and area fraction of the substitutional α -Fe compounds are observed to increase with increase in the Mn:Fe ratio beyond the optimum limit [14,18]. As far as the validity of replacing the primary AlSi10MnMg alloys with suitable secondary ones is concerned, the HPDC processed AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloys studied by Bösch et al. [11] and Niklas et al. [14] have shown mechanical properties within a range as exhibited by their primary counterparts. Owing to limited data on secondary alloys available in the literature, quite recently we endeavored to validate the microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of an HPDC processed AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy with a novel chemical composition [19]. The investigation indicated that our secondary alloy has the potential to achieve the strength and ductility within the range exerted by the commercial primary alloy, however, the properties displayed by our alloy were restricted by the “skin” layer that was inhomogeneously formed on the casting surface.

Now directing our attention towards the “skin” layer, it is a typical microstructure consisting of fine-grained α -Al phase that is imparted on the cast parts by virtue of homogeneous nucleation and rapid solidification at the die surface [20]. Further literature review indicates that even though the formation of such skin layer in HPDC castings has been reported to be substantially inhomogeneous [21–23], it is, more often than investigated, presumably considered to be continuous. Thus, the probable heterogeneity in skin formation and its subsequent effect on the tensile properties exhibited by the HPDC castings have arguably been overlooked, as can be identified in several of the published research works [20,24–27]. Here another question that arises is, pertaining to the tensile properties and fracture mechanism exhibited by the HPDC alloys, how much influential such inhomogeneous skin layer could be as compared to other casting defects that are usually produced during the HPDC process.

When it comes to the influence of casting defects on the tensile properties of HPDC processed primary Al-Si-Mn-Mg alloy system and its secondary variants, porosity is considered to be the most significant contributor. There are two types of pores formed in the HPDC castings of such alloys: (i) Gas pores: During the casting process, when Al reacts with H₂O present as the humidity in the air, it forms Al-oxide and releases H₂ gas which can then get dispersed in the melt to be later appeared as gas pores; (ii) Shrinkage pores: Upon solidification of Al melt, the solid phase shrinks and usually takes up 5 % less volume than

the molten phase, thus resulting in asymmetrical shaped cavities known as shrinkage pores. The ductility exerted by the HPDC alloy has been correlated to the volume fraction [27] and size [28] of the largest pore as well as to the local area fraction of the porosity [29]. More precisely, the tensile properties are improved by a decrease in the porosity fraction and size [30,31]. It has also been observed that the amount and size of pores increase with increase in the thickness of the HPDC castings [29]. As far as the fracture mechanism driven by the porosity is concerned, Jiao et al. [26] explained that the initiation and propagation of micro-cracks take place via expansion, consolidation and collapse of shrinkage pores where the pre-existing small-sized gas pores play a vital role in connecting the large-scale shrinkage pores. Similarly, Liu et al. [27] claimed that the fracture takes place preferentially at the location where the largest pore is present in the gauge section. Another important factor reducing the ductility of the HPDC alloys is the cold flake [32]. When the hot molten metal is poured into relatively cold shot sleeve and subsequently pushed into the die cavity, some of the initially solidified layer in the shot sleeve are broken into small parts and get distributed in the molten metal, which are later observed as cold flakes. This type of defect can act as a pre-existing crack in the material, thereby leading to earlier tensile failure [33]. Having said that, when the oxide layer associated with the cold flake is parallel or slightly inclined from the tensile direction, the cold flake has no major effect on the tensile strength [34]. Other than the pores and cold flakes, there are also reports of α -Fe intermetallic compounds being the stress concentration source, thereby promoting the generation and propagation of micro-cracks resulting in brittle failure of the HPDC alloys [27,35,36]. Pertaining to different loading conditions, the mechanical properties of AlSi10MnMg alloy have been observed to increase slightly with increase in the strain rate from 0.001 to 500 s⁻¹, although the increase was not constant [37].

The above assessment reveals that even though the literature includes reports about the effects of casting defects on the tensile properties exhibited by HPDC processed primary alloy, and some secondary variants of it, no studies were found to evaluate and compare those defects based on their degree of influence. Moreover, the mechanism behind the inhomogeneous formation of surface skin as well as its effects on the ductility behavior of HPDC castings are less explored till date. In addition, there is no study in the literature reporting the tensile behavior and fracture mechanism followed by HPDC processed secondary alloy under higher loading rates which is a crucial factor to consider for automotive structures in crash scenarios. In order to get closer to the goal of finding a suitable secondary alloy to be used in the HPDC process for manufacturing the structural parts of automobiles, these research gaps need to be addressed. Thus, the aim of the current work is to investigate the evolution and effect of microstructure and casting defects on the ductility and fracture behavior of an HPDC processed AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy with varied casting thickness. As pores have so far been considered to be the most important factor in the failure of HPDC castings, the analysis pertaining to these defects is given main attention in the current study. Additionally, the effect of strain rate on the tensile properties and fracture behavior of the secondary alloy is also examined.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Recycled secondary alloy

The recycled secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy used in the current work was supplied by Raffmetal. Table 1 lists the chemical composition of the alloy provided by the supplier. For a quantitative comparison, the composition limits of a primary trimal®-05 AlSi10MnMg alloy produced by Trimet [38] is also included in the table. The Fe and Cu contents in our secondary alloy can be observed to be higher than the limits recommended for the primary alloy. The surplus amount of Fe and Cu in this case is reasonable as these are very commonly found substances in different products which have been recycled to produce the secondary

Table 1

Chemical composition of studied secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy as compared to that of primary alloy (in wt%).

Alloy type	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Ti	Zn	Sr
Secondary alloy	9.547	0.297	0.056	0.65	0.218	0.088	0.03	0.0175
Primary alloy	9.5–11.0	< 0.25	< 0.05	0.4–0.8	0.1–0.45	0.03–0.15	< 0.07	< 0.027

alloy.

2.2. High pressure die casting process

The HPDC castings of AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy were produced by Eurecat. Fig. 1 (a) shows a diagram of the HPDC configuration with different parts. The casting process employed a Bühler cold chamber HPDC machine with a maximum locking force of 5250 kN, a plunger with a diameter of 60 mm, and a stroke of 450 mm. First, around 300 kg of the selected alloy was melted in an electric furnace with a graphite crucible. Then, the melt was treated with Pyroflux salt from Pyrotek, and N₂ gas was bubbled through a porous lance. The molten metal was extracted from the furnace at a temperature between 700 and 720 °C and was poured into the shot sleeve with the help of an automatic ladle. In the first phase of the injection process, the plunger was constantly accelerated to reduce the gas entrapment. The second phase was the filling of the die cavity where the plunger velocity was kept constant at 4 m/s to ensure the filling of the thinnest step with wall thickness of 1 mm. During this die filling stage, the approximate metal velocity at the ingate section having dimensions of 108 mm length and 2.5 mm width was calculated to be 42 m/s. A VDS vacuum system, activated and deactivated by interaction with HPDC machine, was used to remove entrapped air from the die cavity. A ProVac CV 300 chill vent was employed to achieve a vacuum level between 85 and 100 mbars which also promoted the proper filling of the die. The third phase, i.e., the compression phase, started when the plunger felt a backpressure. The

metal pressure was then rapidly increased up to a level between 900 and 950 bars that was kept for 8 s until the solidification of the HPDC part was fully completed. Fig. 1 (b) and (c) respectively represent the top and side view of the as-cast parts having breadth of 170 mm and wall thicknesses of 1-, 2-, 4-, 6-, 10- and 15-mm. The width of each step was 30 mm. Referring to Fig. 1, here it should be highlighted that the gate in the HPDC configuration was located at the bottom of 15 mm thick step whereas the vacuum channels were located above the overflow present next to 1 mm thick step.

2.3. Microstructure analysis

For microstructure analysis, the specimens were cut at different locations such as center and towards the sides of 2-, 4-, 6- and 10-mm thick steps from several as-cast parts and were hot mounted using Polyfast resin to look at their cross-sections. As an example, a 2 mm thick step part is schematically presented in Fig. 2 where the green boxes indicate the cross sections used for microstructure observation. The mounted samples were first mechanically ground using P120, P240, P600, P1200, P2500 and P4000 grit SiC paper, followed by polishing with 1- μ m diamond suspension and 0.05- μ m colloidal silica (OPS) solution. A Nikon Eclipse MA200 light optical microscope (OM) was used to capture optical images on the polished surfaces without any etching.

2.4. X-ray microtomography

In order to find out any plausible correlation between the casting thickness and the amount of porosity induced, X-ray microtomography (XMT) was carried out on HPDC step parts with different thickness. The samples for XMT analysis were machined centrally in the 2-, 6- and 10-mm thick steps from one as-cast part in the shape of tensile specimens. The intention behind it was to perform uniaxial tensile tests on the same samples after the porosity analysis so as to (a) discern the relationship between the tensile properties and the porosity level, and (b) be able to observe the effect of porosity on the deformation behavior, if there could be any, through subsequent fracture analysis. Fig. 3 (a) shows the schematic diagram indicating the dimensions of the tensile specimens, with Fig. 3 (b) displaying the image of the actual tensile sample of 2 mm wall thickness.

Part of the entire gauge section of the three tensile samples having thickness of 2-, 6- and 10-mm were scanned using a Zeiss Xradia 620 Versa XMT system. The scans were taken with the help of a 0.4 \times -detector with no binning, resulting in a field-of-view (FOV) of 13.3 mm and a spatial resolution (voxel size) of 6.5 μ m. The scan settings varied for

Fig. 1. (a) Diagram of HPDC configuration showing different parts, (b) Top view of an actual cast part, and (c) Side view of an actual cast part showing the steps with wall thickness of 1-, 2-, 4-, 6-, 10- and 15-mm. (Adapted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]).

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of an as-cast part of 2 mm step thickness, with green boxes indicating the locations used for analysis using optical microscopy. The pink arrows indicate the two casting surfaces on which the skin layer is supposedly formed. (Adapted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic diagram showing the dimensions of specimen used for uniaxial tensile tests and X-ray microtomography, and (b) The actual tensile specimen of 2 mm wall thickness used for the tests. (Adapted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]).

the three samples due to the variation in their thickness and are listed in Table 2. The tomography reconstruction was carried out using Zeiss reconstruction software (Filtered Back Projection algorithm) with standard settings for artefact correction/removal. The 3D visualization and quantitative analysis were carried out using Dragonfly Pro v2022.2 software. The voids were segmented using standard Otsu thresholding procedure. A “pore” was defined by setting up a condition for the voids with at least 8 voxels need to be connected in 3D. Henceforth, the terms “voids” and “pores” are used interchangeably in the images and texts.

2.5. Uniaxial tensile tests

Two sets of uniaxial tensile tests were performed, as summarized in Table 3: (i) To study the effect of strain rate on the tensile properties: As the recent structural castings in industrial applications are extremely thin-walled in the order of 1.5–2.5 mm, the tensile tests in this case were conducted on several samples of 2 mm thickness with strain rates of 0.001, 0.1 and 10 s⁻¹; (ii) To study the effect of casting thickness/porosity level on the tensile properties: In this case, tensile tests were performed on the three specimens with thickness of 2-, 6- and 10- mm, that were used for XMT earlier, with a strain rate of 0.001 s⁻¹.

The geometry of the tensile specimens is already presented in Fig. 3 (a). Before carrying out the tests, the casting surfaces as well as the gauge thickness of both sets of tensile specimens were ground with P1200 grit SiC paper without removing much of the skin layer from the two casting surfaces (the surfaces on which the skin layer is supposedly formed are indicated by pink arrows in the graphical representation shown in Fig. 2). The purpose of this grinding was to achieve the same final surface roughness as of some other tensile samples that were tested without the skin layer in our earlier study [19], in which case the surfaces of the samples were ground off sequentially with P120, P240, P600 and P1200 grit SiC paper to remove the skin layer.

Table 2

Scanning parameters used for the XMT of three HPDC samples with different wall thickness.

Thickness of sample (mm)	FOV (mm)	Voxel size (μm)	Tube voltage (kV)	Tube output (W)	Zeiss X-ray filter	No of projections	Exposure time (s)	Scan time (h)
2	13.3	6.5	70	8.5	LE4	3201	7.5	9.0
6	13.3	6.5	70	8.5	LE4	3201	8.0	9.5
10	13.3	6.5	80	10	LE5	3201	6.0	7.5

Table 3

Different conditions used for the uniaxial tensile tests of HPDC castings.

Description	Thickness of tensile sample (mm)	Strain rate (s ⁻¹)
Effect of strain rate	2	0.001, 0.1, 10
Effect of casting thickness/porosity	2, 6, 10	0.001

An Instron 1272 servo-hydraulic machine with an Epsilon extensometer having a gauge length of 25 mm was run at crosshead speeds of 0.033 and 2.5 mm/s to achieve the engineering strain rates of 0.001 and 0.1 s⁻¹, respectively. The high-speed testing with strain rate in the order of 10 s⁻¹ was performed using an Instron VHS 160/100–20 hydraulic testing machine, with a Zimmer 100D non-contacting displacement transducer to measure the elongation corresponding to a gauge length of 30 mm. A Phantom V2512 high-speed camera with a sampling rate of approximately 96,000 frames per second was used to take images during the tests of 2 mm thick samples with 0.001 s⁻¹ strain rate (the ones studied for the effect of strain rate) in order to capture the location of crack initiation. Those images were later used for fracture analysis.

2.6. Fracture analysis

For analyzing the deformation mechanism, the fractured surfaces of the deformed specimens were first observed with the help of secondary electrons (SE) and Everhart-Thornley detector (ETD) in an FEI Magellan 400 field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM) with extreme high resolution (XHR) at an accelerating voltage of 3 kV and beam current of 0.8 nA. Then the Nikon OM was used to capture optical images on the lateral surface, which was parallel to the loading direction and whose width corresponded to the thickness of the casting, after carrying out the metallographic sample preparation as described in Section 2.3.

3. Results

3.1. Microstructure evolution in the HPDC processed secondary alloy

3.1.1. Formation of different phases

Fig. 4 shows the characteristic microstructure formed in the as-cast AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy consisting of following three features:

- (i) Primary α-Al: Two types of primary α-Al are observed. (α-Al)_I is the first primary one, formed in the shot sleeve and has a size of > ~20 mm. (α-Al)_{II} is the second primary one which is formed in the die cavity and is smaller in size (< ~10 mm) due to the high cooling rate in the cavity than in the sleeve.
- (ii) α-Fe intermetallic compounds: Three types of α-Fe intermetallics are found. (α-Fe)_I are the first primary ones formed in the shot sleeve, just similar to the (α-Al)_I. They usually have a size of > ~10 mm. (α-Fe)_{II} are the second primary ones formed in the die cavity, similar to the (α-Al)_{II}, and have smaller size of < ~5 mm. The third type of α-Fe compounds manifest a “Chinese script” like structure and seem to be propagating along the interdendritic spaces of α-Al in association with the eutectic growth [39]. Moreover, this Chinese structure observed in 2D is discerned to

Fig. 4. OM image showing characteristic features formed in the as-cast AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy. (Reprinted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]).

comprise convoluted arms in 3D [39]. All the three α -Fe compounds are considered as $\text{Al}_{15}(\text{FeMn})_3\text{Si}_2$ phases [9,11,39,40].

- (iii) Al–Si eutectics: These two-phase eutectics form after the primary phases have been formed.

The most important finding in this case was, even if the Fe content in our recycled secondary alloy is more than the maximum limit recommended in case of primary AlSi10MnMg alloy (referring to Table 1), the OM observation did not reveal any needle or platelet shaped precipitates which usually correspond to β -Fe intermetallics [39,41,42]. So, it can be inferred that the Mn:Fe ratio of 2.1 used in the studied alloy was effective enough to avoid the formation of β -Fe compounds by forming the α -Fe intermetallics instead.

3.1.2. Formation of skin layer with respect to casting thickness

The OM images shown in Fig. 5 exemplify the formation of fine-grained skin layer with respect to the casting thickness. The skin structure produced by the HPDC process in 2- and 4-mm thick castings are

represented in Fig. 5 (a) and (b), respectively. The thickness of skin formed in 2 mm thick step parts is observed to vary between 30 and 150 μm , whereas that in 4 mm thick step parts varies between 20 and 90 μm . On the other hand, as opposed to the general presumption that HPDC always induces skin layers at the casting surfaces, the thicker castings of 6- and 10-mm in our case are devoid of the fine-grained skin structure, as illustrated in Fig. 5 (c) and (d), respectively.

3.1.3. Inhomogeneity in skin formation

Even though the HPDC process imparted fine-grained skin layer on the casting surfaces of 2- and 4-mm thick step parts, this layer is significantly inhomogeneous, meaning that it was not formed continuously throughout on the casting surfaces. Sometimes parts of the two casting surfaces lack the skin structure. And in some other cases, the skin layer is observed to move through the depth of the casting away from the surface and then coming to an end, as illustrated by the red dashed lines in the OM image of a 2 mm thick casting shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5. OM images showing the presence or absence of skin at the casting surface of as-cast AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy having wall thickness of: (a) 2 mm, (b) 4 mm, (c) 6 mm, and (d) 10 mm.

Fig. 6. OM image of a 2 mm thick as-cast step part showing an inhomogeneous skin layer, where the skin appears to be migrating through the thickness of the casting and ending abruptly, as indicated by the red dashed lines. (Adapted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.1.4. Defects formed during the HPDC process

Two of the casting defects found in the as-cast parts of HPDC processed AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy are shown in Fig. 7. Fig. 7 (a) displays a cold flake which is identified on a 2D OM image by a sudden change in the microstructural features across a straight flat boundary, as indicated by the red arrows in the image. The morphology is switched from a mixture of relatively globular α -Al and Al–Si eutectics, belonging to the metal matrix, to fine columnar α -Al elongated in multi direction, belonging to the defect. The grains inside the cold flake close to the flake boundary are much smaller than the ones away from it. The flake boundary, appearing as a straight line on an OM image, essentially designates a poor joining between the flake particle and the metal matrix across a flat surface in 3D. The variation in the microstructure across this flat surface indicates the variation in the cooling rate for cold flake solidified in the shot sleeve and that for the matrix solidified in the die cavity. Sometimes the flat surface of the flake is accompanied by an oxide layer on it [34,43] which was not discerned in our case.

The second type of defect shown here is a cold shot (Fig. 7 (b)) which is identified by a unique mixture of nearly globular and small elongated morphology that is conspicuously in contrast with the surrounding matrix. Cold shots are small drops of solidified globules which are formed due to the turbulence inside the die cavity during the casting process. When the velocity of molten metal at the ingate is very high, liquid metal streams are shot out into the die cavity as spray and when they hit the die core, small drops of cold shots may develop which solidify much faster than the surrounding main molten metal.

Furthermore, it is found that the number and size of the two abovementioned casting defects increase with increase in the casting thickness. As an example, the trend of the size for the cold flakes observed in our HPDC castings of 2- and 10- mm wall thickness is illustrated in Fig. 8. It can be discerned that the flat edge of the cold flake

(indicated by red dashed lines in Fig. 8) formed in the 10 mm thick step part (Fig. 8 (b)) is longer than that in the 2 mm thick step part (Fig. 8 (a)). Moreover, the entire cold flake in 2 mm thick casting, outlined by red and black dashed lines in Fig. 8 (a), could be captured in a single frame under OM. Whereas, at the same magnification, only a small part of the cold flake found in 10 mm thick casting could be captured in a single frame (Fig. 8 (b)).

The HPDC castings of our secondary alloy also contain large number of porosity which is analyzed and presented separately later in Section 3.4.

3.2. Tensile behavior with respect to varied strain rate

Fig. 9 (a) shows the engineering stress vs engineering strain curves obtained from the uniaxial tensile tests of 2 mm thick specimens carried out with 0.001, 0.1 and 10 s^{-1} strain rates. Here total nine curves are plotted in one graph, with three samples tested at each strain rate. For the simplicity of presentation and explanation, the curves corresponding to the samples tested with 0.001 s^{-1} strain rate are designated as A, B and C (green in color), the ones tested with 0.1 s^{-1} strain rate are designated as D, E and F (purple in color), and the ones tested with 10 s^{-1} strain rate are indicated as G, H and I (red in color). For a better illustration of the ductility exhibited by the secondary alloy, the total elongation (TE) obtained from the stress-strain curves are plotted with respect to the three strain rates in Fig. 9 (b). The following observations are made from these figures:

- (i) All samples, irrespective of the strain rate, failed before reaching their “necking” point, which is inferred by the absence of the plateau at the peak of stress-strain curves (Fig. 9 (a)).
- (ii) A relatively large variation in the ductility can be observed in case of each strain rate (Fig. 9 (b)), which is attributed to the fact that the corresponding specimens in each case failed at inconsistent elongations (Fig. 9 (a)).
- (iii) In case of samples tested with 0.001 s^{-1} strain rate, samples B and C followed more or less the same flow stress path as of sample A but failed at different lower elongations (Fig. 9 (a)). As a result, the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of samples B and C were restricted from reaching up to the level exhibited by sample A. Such trend of ductility and UTS can also be observed in case of samples tested with 0.1 and 10 s^{-1} strain rates.
- (iv) The flow stress of the material arguably increased, though not very significantly, with increase in the strain rate (Fig. 9 (a)).
- (v) The tensile tests at 10 s^{-1} strain rate can be perceived to experience dynamic effects due to the high loading rate, as indicated by the small wavy steps formed on their corresponding stress-strain curves (Fig. 9 (a)).

Regardless of the strain rate, the large variation in ductility

Fig. 7. OM images showing the casting defects produced in the as-cast AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy: (a) Cold flake with conspicuous flat edge indicated by red arrows, and (b) Cold shot. (Adapted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Cold flakes observed in the HPDC castings having step thickness of (a) 2 mm, and (b) 10 mm. The red dashed line in each image indicates the flat edge of the cold flake particle. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. (a) Engineering stress vs engineering strain curves obtained from the uniaxial tensile tests of 2 mm thick HPDC AlSi10MnMg(Fe) specimens deformed with 0.001, 0.1 and 10 s⁻¹ strain rates, and (b) Corresponding total elongation (TE) undergone by each specimen.

demonstrated by the HPDC processed secondary alloy necessitated the fracture analysis of all the deformed specimens which is presented in the next section.

3.3. Fracture behavior with respect to varied strain rate

3.3.1. Crack initiation in samples tested with 0.001 s⁻¹ strain rate

Fig. 10 depicts the fracture analysis conducted on samples that were tested with 0.001 s⁻¹ strain rate. Fig. 10 (a), (d) and (g) respectively display the images captured by the high-speed camera during the testing of samples A, B and C, where the yellow arrow indicates the crack initiation in each case. It can be observed that in all samples the crack initiated from one of the edges within the gauge section. These images were then used to determine the location of crack initiation on the fracture surface of the respective deformed specimen for observation under the SEM. Thus, Fig. 10 (b), (e) and (h) display the SEM images of the crack initiation areas, highlighted by yellow dashed rectangles, captured on the fracture surface of samples A, B and C, respectively. The initiation of failure at these locations can be discerned by the local brittle behavior, characterized by their smooth surface (present within the yellow box) as compared to the rest of the matrix. Moreover, the smooth surface of crack initiation area in sample C can be observed to delineate from the adjacent matrix via a clear fringe, as indicated by the blue arrows in Fig. 10 (h), suggesting a delamination of metal matrix across the fracture surface. Fig. 10 (c) and (f) display the OM images taken on the lateral surface adjacent to the corresponding crack initiation area in samples A and B, respectively. Whereas Fig. 10 (i) shows the entire lateral surface of deformed sample C with yellow arrow indicating the side of crack initiation. Both samples B and C possessed skin layer on the casting surface adjacent to their respective crack initiation area, as indicated by red dashed lines in Fig. 10 (f) and (i), respectively. Whereas

the casting surface close to the crack initiation area of sample A did not contain any skin layer (Fig. 10 (c)). Such absence of skin structure is a demonstration of the discontinuity in skin formation as mentioned earlier in Section 3.1.3.

3.3.2. Crack initiation in samples tested with 0.1 s⁻¹ strain rate

Fig. 11 depicts the fracture analysis conducted on samples that were tested with 0.1 s⁻¹ strain rate. As the crack initiation area in the samples tested with 0.001 s⁻¹ strain rate always featured a local brittle behavior when looked under the SEM (referring to Fig. 10 (b), (e) and (h)), this trend was subsequently considered to locate the crack initiation area on the fracture surface of samples tested with 0.1 s⁻¹ strain rates. Thus, the SEM images taken on the deformed samples D, E and F are respectively presented in Fig. 11 (a), (c) and (e), with yellow dashed rectangle in each image highlighting the local brittle behavior at one of the corners, thereby indicating the crack initiation, just like the pattern observed in case of samples tested with 0.001 s⁻¹ strain rate. In samples E and F, the brittle crack initiation area featured a clear fringe of delamination, as indicated by the blue arrows in Fig. 11 (c) and (e), respectively, similar to the one found in sample C tested with a strain rate of 0.001 s⁻¹ (referring to Fig. 10 (h)). Fig. 11 (b), (d) and (f) display the OM images taken on the lateral surface adjacent to the corresponding crack initiation area in samples D, E and F, respectively. The red dashed lines in the respective images manifest the presence of skin layer on the casting surface next to the crack initiation area in all three specimens.

3.3.3. Crack initiation in samples tested with 10 s⁻¹ strain rate

Fig. 12 depicts the fracture analysis conducted on tensile samples that were tested with 10 s⁻¹ strain rate. Similar to the analysis carried out on the specimens deformed with 0.1 s⁻¹ strain rate, the fracture surface of samples deformed with 10 s⁻¹ strain rate were also examined

Fig. 10. Fracture analysis of HPDC tensile specimens tested with 0.001 s^{-1} strain rate: (a – c) Sample A, (d – f) Sample B, and (g – i) Sample C. (a), (d) and (g) are the images captured by the high-speed optical camera during the tensile tests, with yellow arrows indicating the crack initiation. (b), (e) and (h) are the SEM images taken on the fracture surface of the deformed samples, with yellow dashed boxes indicating their corresponding crack initiation area, and blue arrows in (h) indicating a fringe of delamination. (c), (f) and (i) are the OM images taken on the lateral surface adjacent to the corresponding crack initiation area in the deformed samples, with orange arrow in each image indicating the loading direction. The yellow arrow and the purple dashed line in (i) indicate the crack initiation side and the flat cold flake boundary, respectively. The red dashed lines in (f) and (i) indicate the skin layer. (adapted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

under SEM to identify the brittle features that could plausibly account for the crack initiation. No such local brittle behavior could be found in case of sample G. Instead, a number of large shrinkage pores was observed on its fracture surface, one of which is displayed in Fig. 12 (a). Whereas conspicuous brittle behavior discerning the crack initiation could be detected at one of the corners in case of both samples H and I, as indicated by the yellow dashed rectangle in Fig. 12 (c) and (e), respectively. Pertaining to the OM analysis, in case of deformed samples H and I, the images were captured on their lateral surface adjacent to their respective crack initiation area, which are presented in Fig. 12 (d) and (f), respectively. Whereas, since the crack initiation area in sample G could not be discerned from its SEM analysis, the OM image was captured on a randomly chosen lateral surface, which is displayed in Fig. 12 (b). The red dashed lines in Fig. 12 (b), (d) and (f) manifest the presence of skin layer on the casting surface next to the crack in all three specimens, just as similar to the samples tested with 0.1 s^{-1} strain rate.

3.4. Porosity with respect to varied casting thickness

3.4.1. 3D XMT images of porosity

The 3D images obtained from the XMT of three HPDC samples with 2-, 6- and 10-mm wall thickness are displayed in Fig. 13. The color

coding in the XMT images indicate the volume of pores in mm^3 . The blue and brown color respectively denote smallest and largest pores, whereas other colors, such as green, yellow and red, designate pores with intermediate volume. All the samples can be observed to contain two types of pores:

- (i) *Gas pores*: which appear blueish in color and have more or less a spherical morphology.
- (ii) *Shrinkage pores*: which appear more green, yellow, red and brown in color with comparatively irregular shapes.

In each sample, the size of the shrinkage pores can be seen to be larger than that of the gas pores.

3.4.2. Number density and volume fraction of pores

In order to have an accurate comparison about the amount of pores induced in the HPDC castings of different thickness, the number density of pores per unit volume along with their corresponding volume fraction are plotted with respect to the casting thickness in one graph, which is presented in Fig. 14. The number density in case of 2- and 6-mm thick casting is found to be 22 and 21 pores per mm^3 , respectively. And the volume fraction of pores in both of them is 0.1 %. Thus, the amount of

Fig. 11. Fracture analysis of HPDC tensile specimens tested with 0.1 s^{-1} strain rate: (a, b) Sample D, (c, d) Sample E, and (e, f) Sample F. (a), (c) and (e) are the SEM images taken on the fracture surface of the deformed samples, with yellow dashed box in each case indicating the corresponding crack initiation area, and blue arrows in (c) and (e) indicating fringe of delamination. (b), (d) and (f) are the OM images taken on the lateral surface adjacent to the corresponding crack initiation area in the deformed samples, with orange arrow and red dashed lines respectively indicating the loading direction and skin layer in each case. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

pores formed in the 2- and 6-mm thick HPDC step parts are quite comparable with each other. Whereas the number density and volume fraction of the pores are observed to increase to 52 pores per mm^3 and 0.8 %, respectively, in the 10 mm thick step.

3.4.3. Pore size distribution

In order to further analyze the observed trend of number density and volume fraction, the equivalent diameters of pores were calculated, and their normalized distribution (counts per unit volume) was plotted with respect to casting thickness, which is shown in Fig. 15. The green, blue and red arrows in Fig. 15 (a) indicate the largest equivalent diameters among all the pores respectively found in 2-, 6- and 10-mm thick castings. It can be inferred that the largest equivalent diameter increases with increase in the casting thickness. The 6 mm thick casting can be observed to contain some pores that are bigger than the largest pore found in the 2 mm thick casting, as indicated by the equivalent diameters ranging between the green and blue arrow marks in Fig. 15 (a). However, a closer look at the magnified distribution shown in Fig. 15 (b) reveals a higher count for some of the small pores corresponding to equivalent diameter less than $100 \mu\text{m}$ in case of 2 mm thick casting as compared to its 6 mm thick counterpart, thereby ultimately leading to the same overall number density and volume fraction of pores in the two

castings (referring to Fig. 14). As compared to 2- and 6-mm thick castings, the 10 mm thick casting contains a higher pore count corresponding to each equivalent diameter (referring to Fig. 15 (b)) along with pores having larger equivalent diameters (referring to Fig. 15 (a)), thus resulting in an increased number density and volume fraction of pores as manifested in Fig. 14.

3.5. Tensile behavior with respect to varied casting thickness

Fig. 16 displays the engineering stress vs engineering strain curves obtained from the uniaxial tensile tests conducted on 2-, 6- and 10-mm thick specimens (the same specimens that were earlier used for porosity analysis) at a strain rate of 0.001 s^{-1} and plotted in one graph. Here it should be reiterated that the purpose of conducting tensile tests on only one specimen from each thickness was to study the effects from pores present in the individual specimens. The following observations are made from Fig. 16:

- (i) All samples, irrespective of their thickness, failed before reaching the “necking” point, just as similar to what is observed for the tensile tests with different strain rates (referring to Fig. 9 (a)).

Fig. 12. Fracture analysis of HPDC tensile specimens tested with 10 s^{-1} strain rate: (a, b) Sample G, (c, d) Sample H, and (e, f) Sample I. (a), (c) and (e) are the SEM images taken on the fracture surface of the deformed samples, with yellow dashed box in (c) and (e) indicating the respective crack initiation area. (b), (d) and (f) are the OM images taken on the lateral surface of the deformed samples, with orange arrow and red dashed lines respectively indicating the loading direction and skin layer in each case. (d) and (f) correspond to the lateral surface adjacent to the respective crack initiation area, whereas (b) corresponds to a lateral surface that was chosen randomly. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

- (ii) The 2 mm thick sample exhibited a little higher yield strength (YS) at 0.2 % offset (120 MPa) as compared to its 6- and 10-mm thick counterparts (108 and 100 MPa, respectively).
- (iii) There is a conspicuous variation in the TE with respect to casting thickness. Initially the ductility was anticipated to be the least for 10 mm thick sample since it was seen to contain the most amount of porosity among the three tested thicknesses as presented in Section 3.4. However, surprisingly, the least ductility is observed to be exhibited by 2 mm thick sample, whereas 10 mm thick sample exhibited the highest ductility. This unexpected behavior required the fracture analysis of all three deformed specimens which is presented next.

3.6. Fracture behavior with respect to varied casting thickness

3.6.1. Fracture surface analysis using SEM

Fig. 17 presents the SEM images taken on the fracture surface of the tensile specimens tested for different casting thickness. The 2 mm thick casting displayed a clear brittle feature at one of the corners of the deformed specimen, as highlighted by the yellow dashed rectangle in Fig. 17 (a), which indicated the initiation of fracture. Moreover, a fringe of delamination could be observed in this case, as outlined by the blue

arrows on the image. It can be noticed that the delamination pattern seen here is different, rather to be more precise, imaginably complementary to the patterns observed on the fracture surface of other 2 mm thick deformed specimens which are shown in Fig. 10 (h), Fig. 11 (c) and (e). Therefore, it was decided to analyze the two fractured parts belonging to the current sample by mounting them together in a way so as to jointly look at their lateral surfaces adjacent to the crack initiation area, which is presented in the next section. Moving on to the 6 mm thick specimen, it displayed a huge flat area on its fracture surface as highlighted by the red dashed portion in Fig. 17 (b). Such flat rupture implied a very poor joining and an abrupt detachment of the surfaces. Therefore, it was decided to look at the adjoining lateral surfaces across the flat rupture by mounting the two fractured parts together (in a similar way as mentioned above for the 2 mm thick sample), which is presented in the next section. When it comes to the fracture in 10 mm thick casting, unlike in 2- and 6-mm thick samples, there was no noticeable feature on the fracture surface that could reveal the crack initiation. However, the said surface exhibited a great number of large shrinkage pores, which is discerned by the surrounding dendritic arms of α -Al phase. Such characteristic appearance of one shrinkage pore is displayed in Fig. 17 (c), with yellow arrows in the image indicating the α -Al dendritic arms. Both the size and number of shrinkage pores observed on the fracture surface

Fig. 13. XMT images showing porosity distribution in the HPDC samples having wall thickness of (a) 2 mm, (b) 6 mm, and (c) 10 mm. The legend in each image indicates the volume of pores in mm³.

Fig. 14. Number density and fraction of pores induced in the HPDC castings of different wall thickness.

of 10 mm thick sample were conspicuously lot higher than the ones found on that of 2- and 6-mm thick samples, which is aligned with the aforementioned trend from the XMT analysis reported in Section Section 3.4.

It could be inferred from the SEM analysis that the fracture in 10 mm thick sample was driven by the porosity present in the casting. Whereas further investigation was required to determine the exact cause behind the fracture behavior observed in case of the other two samples, which is presented next.

3.6.2. Lateral surface analysis using OM

Fig. 18 (a) shows the OM image taken on the lateral surfaces of the two fractured parts of 2 mm thick tensile sample. The yellow arrow mark

in the image approximates the location of the brittle feature earlier presented in Fig. 17 (a). The magnified image of this location enclosed by the green rectangle in Fig. 18 (a) shows the formation of surface skin layer in the parent specimen, as highlighted by the red dashed lines in Fig. 18 (c). More interestingly, this skin layer seems to have been ceased across the fractured surface, which can be deduced by the absence of the layer at the adjacent location on the other part of the fractured specimen shown in Fig. 18 (b). Thus, it can be seen that, in the parent undeformed specimen, the skin is formed through the thickness away from the casting surface and then suddenly ceases to exist at a point, resembling the anomalous skin formation presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 19 (a) shows the OM image taken on the lateral surfaces of the two fractured parts of 6 mm thick tensile sample. The red arrow mark in the image approximates the location of the flat rupture earlier presented in Fig. 17 (b). The magnified image of the associated straight edge enclosed by the red rectangle in Fig. 19 (a) reveals a sudden change in the microstructure across the flat rupture (Fig. 19 (b)). Such microstructure alteration is a characteristic feature of the cold flake as described in Section 3.1.4. Here, as can be observed in Fig. 19 (b), the morphology is switched from a mixture of relatively globular and dendritic α -Al phase, belonging to the material matrix, to fine columnar α -Al phase elongated in multi direction, belonging to the cold flake.

Here it can be mentioned that since the initial OM investigation did not reveal any skin pattern on the surface of several 10 mm thick castings that were analyzed (referring to Section 3.1.2), it was not deemed pertinent to perform OM analysis on the lateral surface of 10 mm thick tensile specimen.

3.7. Common features observed on fracture surface

The fracture surface analysis using SEM also revealed varieties of microstructural features in both sets of deformed specimens, i.e., the ones tested with different strain rates as well as the ones tested for

Fig. 15. (a) Normalized distribution of pores size, in terms of equivalent diameter, for different casting thickness. The green, blue and red arrows indicate the largest equivalent diameter of pores found in 2-, 6- and 10-mm thick castings, respectively. (b) is the magnified profile of the porosity distribution indicated by black dashed rectangle in (a). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 16. Engineering stress vs engineering strain curves obtained from the uniaxial tensile tests of specimens having different wall thickness.

different casting thickness, the most important elements of which are presented in Fig. 20. Fig. 20 (a) depicts the regular matrix on the fracture surface, consisting of primary α -Al and Al–Si eutectic areas indicated by yellow and blue arrows, respectively. The Al–Si eutectic regions are

observed to be cracked during the fracture, as indicated by red arrows in the image of a eutectic area shown in Fig. 20 (b). A highly magnified image of Al–Si eutectics is presented in Fig. 20 (c) where a Si particle embedded within Al solid solution can be observed to have fractured, as indicated by red arrow in the image. Fig. 20 (d – f) show the three α -Fe compounds formed in the secondary alloy, which are easily distinguishable from the surrounding matrix by virtue of their flat, smooth surface and relatively sharp edges. All the Chinese script α -Fe intermetallics found in the tensile tested samples were observed to be cracked. Fig. 20 (d) is an example of such a compound with red arrows indicating the cracks. Some of the $(\alpha\text{-Fe})_I$ and $(\alpha\text{-Fe})_{II}$ particles were cracked during the deformation, as indicated by red arrows in Fig. 20 (e), whereas some others in the same parent specimen remained uncracked, as exemplified in Fig. 20 (f). The α -Fe intermetallics were observed to be present abundantly on the fracture surface of all tensile tested samples.

4. Discussion

4.1. Formation of inhomogeneous surface skin

The HPDC process did not impart skin layer on all over the casting surface of the entire component having different step thickness (referring to Fig. 5). Furthermore, wherever the fine-grained layer was

Fig. 17. SEM images showing the fracture surface of tensile samples having wall thickness of (a) 2 mm, (b) 6 mm, and (c) 10 mm. The yellow dashed rectangle in (a) indicates brittle feature, with blue arrows indicating a fringe of delamination. The red dashed portion in (b) displays a very flat fracture. The yellow arrows in (c) indicate the dendritic arms of α -Al surrounding the shrinkage pore. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 18. (a) OM image showing the lateral surface of the two fractured parts belonging to the tensile sample having 2 mm wall thickness, with the yellow arrow approximating the location of brittle feature displayed in the SEM image of Fig. 17 (a). (b) and (c) are respectively the magnified images of the areas enclosed by pink and green rectangles in (a). The yellow and white arrows in (c) indicate the crack initiation by delamination of skin and the resultant final fracture, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 19. (a) OM image showing the lateral surface of the two fractured parts belonging to the tensile sample having 6 mm wall thickness, with the red arrow indicating the location of flat surface shown in the SEM image of Fig. 17 (b). (b) is the magnified image of the area enclosed by red box in (a). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

observed to be present, it was not formed continuously throughout on the casting surface (as exemplified in Fig. 6). The characteristic formation of such surface skin layer in our HPDC casting is attributed to the melt flow pattern inside the die cavity. The complexity of the flow pattern, which is essentially governed by fluid dynamics, makes it quite difficult to come up with an exact explanation. Nevertheless, the formation of typical skin layer in our case is attempted to explain with the help of Fig. 21 which presents still images at different time steps from the simulation of the die filling stage. The simulation was run using Inspirecast software for a standard primary alloy with conditions as close as possible to the actual casting process. Referring to the simulation images in Fig. 21, the die geometry as presented in Fig. 1 (a) is indicated by blue rectangle along with the steps having different wall thickness. Here it needs to be clarified and emphasized that the usage of these simulation images is just to support the explanation behind the melt flow pattern provided below.

When the molten metal is plunged through the thin ingate at a high velocity (approximating to 42 m/s in our case, as stated in Section 2.2), it enters the die cavity from the bottom of 15 mm thick step (referring to Fig. 21 (a1)) with a high momentum. As a result, when the melt impinges on the die surface inside the cavity close to the ingate, it generates a high impact pressure. Thus, much of the heat from the melt is transferred to the die surface, thereby significantly increasing the local die surface temperature, possibly close to the temperature of the molten metal [44]. Due to the resultant minor temperature gradient, the cooling rate here is much slower. Additionally, in the beginning of the die filling stage, the melt flow is quite turbulent approximately up to 6 mm thick step (referring to Fig. 21 (a1 – a4)). So, even though the melt stream here may cool down to be enriched with some solid fraction, it does not get the time to be stabilized and solidify quickly as the succeeding molten metal keeps on coming in so as to fill in the entire die cavity [23]. Moreover, after the completion of die filling stage, the cooling rate in the

Fig. 20. SEM images on the fractured surfaces of tensile tested samples displaying: (a) matrix of the fractured surface with yellow and blue arrows indicating α -Al phase and Al—Si eutectics, respectively, (b) Al—Si eutectics, (c) fractured Si particle within Al solid solution (adapted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]), (d) cracked Chinese script α -Fe compound, (e) cracked (α -Fe)_I and (α -Fe)_{II} compounds, and (f) uncracked (α -Fe)_I and (α -Fe)_{II} compounds. The red arrows in (b – e) indicate cracks. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 21. Still images from the simulation of die filling stage with increasing time from left to right. (Reprinted with permission from Dalai et al. [19]).

thicker steps is plausibly low. As a combined effect of all the above-mentioned traits, the probability of fine-grained skin layer formation in the steps with thickness of 6 mm and above is negligible. Instead, a mixture of α -Al phase and Al—Si eutectics is solidified at their surface.

Moving on to the filling up of steps thinner than 6 mm, the typical die geometry together with the size and position of the ingate most likely causes a first layer of melt streams to flow along the die surface at different locations (such as the sides and middle) of the 4- and 2-mm thick steps during the filling up of previous thicker steps (referring to Fig. 21 (a3)). As this layer of melt streams is the first one to strike at the die surface of 4- and 2-mm thick steps, much of the heat from the melt is expected to be transferred to the surface, thereby significantly increasing the local die surface temperature. Thus, instead of a fine-grained skin layer, a mixture of α -Al phase and Al—Si eutectics is formed at the surface, as explained in the previous paragraph. Subsequently, these thinner steps continue to be filled up by the succeeding layer of melt streams (referring to Fig. 21 (a4)). These melt streams are believed to have lost some of their heat as well as momentum during their journey over the previously deposited layers in the thicker steps. Thus, when this second layer of melt streams arrives at the die surface, the local die surface temperature remains relatively lower, unlike in case of impingement from the first layer of melt streams. As a result, a relatively large temperature gradient is induced between the die surface and

the melt, thereby promoting a fast cooling rate to form fine-grained skin layer at the surface.

Now, the characteristic inhomogeneous skin pattern, as illustrated in Fig. 6, is feasibly formed when the hot melt stream being solidified as skin layer encounters an already solidified and cooled down layer of α -Al and Al—Si mixture. The phenomenon resembles the formation of “waves and lakes” type of defects in HPDC parts, in which case, when the two melt fronts meet, with one melt being cooler than the other, there is enough heat for remelting the melt fronts to get attached with each other [45]. In our case, when the warmer melt meets the already solidified cooler melt, the former tends to flow on to the surface of the latter while undergoing rapid solidification to form fine grains. When the content of melt being solidified as skin runs out or when the temperature gradient diminishes, thereby ending the rapid solidification, it ultimately appears as if the skin has moved through the thickness and has come to an abrupt termination (as exemplified in Fig. 6). Since such heterogeneous pattern manifests a sort of irregularity induced in the microstructure during the HPDC process, the inhomogeneous skin is therefore suggested to be a casting defect.

4.2. Fracture resulting from inhomogeneous skin

In case of inhomogeneous skin formation, as explained above, since

the skin layer is solidified on to the pre-solidified layer of α -Al and Al—Si mixture, the bonding between these two layers is very weak, which is extant along their interface up to a point where the skin solidification is terminated. Such lack of joining is susceptible to delamination of the layers during the deformation process which can lead to sudden failure of the sample. This behavior is demonstrated in Fig. 18 where the skin layer in the parent specimen is formed adjacent to the pre-solidified α -Al and Al—Si layer, thus appears as migrating through the thickness away from the casting surface (similar to as illustrated in Fig. 6). As a result, the sample experiences a poor joining between the two layers through a depth of $\sim 450\ \mu\text{m}$ (estimated as the distance of the end point of the skin from the initial casting surface). During the tensile test, such large extent of weak joining led to definite crack initiation via severe delamination of skin layer (indicated by yellow arrows in Fig. 18 (c)), which was detrimental enough to trigger an abrupt final fracture (indicated by white arrows in Fig. 18 (c)).

Now, comparing the crack initiation area shown in Fig. 18 (c) with the ones observed in the samples deformed with varied strain rates of 0.001 (samples B and C shown respectively in Fig. 10 (f) and (i)), 0.1 (samples E and F shown respectively in Fig. 11 (d) and (f)) and $10\ \text{s}^{-1}$ (samples H and I shown respectively in Fig. 12 (d) and (f)), a definite similarity in the skin pattern present at the crack initiation area can be discerned. So, it is inferred that each of the samples B, C, E, F, H and I underwent abrupt fracture triggered by the same delamination induced crack as mentioned above because of the poor joining instigated by the inhomogeneous skin layer formed at their respective casting surfaces.

4.3. Detrimental effect of inhomogeneous skin on ductility

Fig. 9 depicts that the 2 mm thick HPDC castings failed at different TE irrespective of the strain rate. Such large variation in the ductility exhibited by the same alloy implies abrupt failure in case of some individual specimens. From the subsequent fracture analysis, it was found that the crack propagation through the sample by means of cracking the Si and α -Fe particles on the way is the same in all deformed samples irrespective of strain rates (referring to Section 3.7). Thus, the abrupt/early failure of different samples is inferred to be related to the initiation of crack in the respective cases. As it is observed from the images captured by the high-speed camera (shown in Fig. 10) and can be inferred from the SEM images (shown in Fig. 10 – Fig. 12), the crack in the samples tested at different strain rates (reported in Section 3.3) always initiated from one of the edges of the gauge section (except for sample G which did not reveal any conspicuous crack initiation area on its fracture surface). The results from the subsequent OM investigation at the said crack initiation edges (shown in Fig. 10 – Fig. 12) revealed the presence/absence of skin layers, with certain inhomogeneity in some cases (as deduced in Section 4.2). Such characteristic of skin layers observed by OM in each deformed specimen is correlated with their corresponding TE and summarized in Fig. 22.

It can be seen from the figure that sample A, which did not contain any skin next to its crack initiation area (Fig. 10 (c)), exhibited the largest TE (6.8 %, referring to Fig. 9 (b)). The samples G and D which contained continuous skin, i.e., the skin layer arguably continuing across the fracture surface (referring to Fig. 12 (b) and Fig. 11 (b), respectively), exhibited a little lower TE (5.8 and 4.4 %, respectively, referring to Fig. 9 (b)). Whereas all the samples that possessed inhomogeneous skin (samples B, C, E, F, H and I, as inferred in Section 4.2), characterized by the fine-grained layer that appears to be migrating through the thickness away from the casting surface, failed at comparatively lower TE between 1.6 and 4.1 % (referring to Fig. 9 (b)). The restricted ductility in these samples can be attributed to the abrupt fracture triggered by the inhomogeneous skin layer as explained in Section 4.2.

4.4. Fracture resulting from cold flake

Fig. 10 (i) displays a part of a cold flake present on the lateral surface

Fig. 22. Type of skin pattern observed close to the crack initiation area in each deformed specimen of HPDC processed AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy tested at different strain rates, summarized in relation to their corresponding total elongation.

of a 2 mm thick tensile sample that was tested with $0.001\ \text{s}^{-1}$ strain rate. In this case, the flat boundary of the cold flake, which typically designates the weak joining between the flake and adjoining matrix across a 3D surface, is parallel to the loading axis, as indicated by the purple dashed lines in the image. As could be observed, the defect did not have any influence whatsoever on the fracture of the material. This demonstrates that the weak joining associated with the cold flake does not play any significant role in driving a fracture if its flat surface is nearly parallel to the loading axis.

By referring to Fig. 19, the flat surface in the SEM image of the deformed sample displayed in Fig. 17 (b) can be deduced to be nothing but the weak surface boundary between the cold flake and the adjacent matrix. In this case, the material underwent a fracture when the flat surface boundary was oriented at approximately 30° from the loading axis (referring to Fig. 19 (a)). It has already been reported that when the cold flake is located within the metal matrix in such a way that its weak surface boundary is perpendicular to the loading axis, the flake particle can very easily be detached from the adjoining matrix during the loading [34]. In our case, the orientation of 30° between the flake boundary and the loading axis was detrimental enough to drive an abrupt fracture through delamination of the defect from the matrix.

4.5. Evolution of shrinkage pores with respect to casting thickness

The relatively large sized pores (equivalent diameter $> \sim 100\ \mu\text{m}$) are characteristically the shrinkage pores, and their abundance in 10 mm thick casting (referring to Fig. 15 (a)) can be explained using the simulation of die filling pattern shown in Fig. 21. During the die filling stage, when the 6- and 2-mm thick step parts start to be gradually filled (referring to Fig. 21 (a2 – a5)) and Al-phases are subsequently solidified in these steps, irregular shaped cavities are developed due to the shrinkage in volume corresponding to the solid phase. As the die filling continues to progress, some of these cavities can plausibly be filled by the incoming melt, thereby restricting the size and density of the shrinkage pores in 2- and 6-mm thick step parts. Moreover, it can be visualized from Fig. 21 (a4 and a5) that the 10- and 15-mm thick steps are the last ones to be completely filled with the molten metal. Thus, when the 10 mm thick step is filled up towards the end of the die filling stage with limited incoming molten metal flow and the melt is gradually solidified to induce shrinkage pores, there is not enough liquid metal available inside the die cavity to be solidified within the pores as much of the melt has arguably been consumed in filling up the cavities produced earlier in the thinner sections (referring to Fig. 21 (a3 – a5)). As a result, the shrinkage pores developed in the 10 mm thick step remain unaltered, thus resulting in their considerably larger size and greater

fraction as compared to in 2- and 6-mm thick steps.

4.6. Order of detrimental effect on ductility caused by the casting defects

The ductility exhibited by the HPDC castings of 2-, 6- and 10-mm wall thickness of our AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy (obtained from Fig. 16) with respect to their microstructure analysis (obtained from Fig. 14 and Fig. 17 – Fig. 20) are summarized in Table 4. The deformation of samples, irrespective of the casting thickness, is earlier shown to crack the α -Fe intermetallics (referring to Fig. 20 (d and e) in Section 3.7), just as similar to what has been reported in the literature [27,35,36]. Moreover, these α -Fe compounds are abundantly present in our HPDC processed alloy of varied casting thickness. Nevertheless, when it comes to the ductility exhibited by the material, these intermetallics do not seem to have any noticeable effect on the ductility (referring to Table 4). In case of porosity induced in the HPDC castings, the 10 mm thick casting contains the largest amount of pores in terms of volume fraction (0.8 %) among the three casting thicknesses and was therefore expected to exhibit the lowest ductility as per the reports [24,26,27] available in the literature. However, it actually exhibited the highest TE of 3.6 % among the three casting thicknesses. Furthermore, even though the pores present in the 2- and 6-mm thick castings are comparable with each other (0.1 % volume fraction in each case) and a lot lower than that present in their 10 mm thick counterpart, their TE was limited to 1.5 and 2.9 %, respectively. Such unexpected restriction of the ductility, considering the comparatively lower porosity levels present in the 2- and 6-mm thick castings, is attributed to the abrupt fracture of the specimens triggered by the delamination which took place because of the inhomogeneous skin in the former (referring to Section 4.2) and the cold flake in the latter (referring to Section 4.4). Referring to the Table 4, it can further be pointed out that when no skin was formed on the casting surface, such as in 6- and 10-mm thick castings (referring to Section 3.1.2), the material could withstand larger TE. Whereas, when the skin was formed on the casting surface following an inhomogeneous pattern, such as in 2 mm thick casting, the ductility of the material was restricted to the lowest TE.

Thus, it can be concluded that the inhomogeneity in the surface skin formed during the HPDC of our secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy poses the most detrimental effect on the ductility of the material, which is followed by the deleterious effect caused by the cold flakes. Having said that, the negative effect of the cold flake is negligible when its flat surface boundary is nearly parallel to the loading direction, and only becomes significant when the boundary is oriented at an angle of more than approximately 30° to the loading direction (referring to Section 4.4). Furthermore, the large-scale shrinkage pores also plausibly limit the ductility of the HPDC alloy, but not as much as the inhomogeneous skin and cold flakes do.

4.7. Scope for further research

The current study manifests that the tensile properties, especially the ductility, exhibited by the HPDC processed alloy are significantly influenced by fracture mechanism driven by the inhomogeneous skin layer. Formation of such typical skin structure has been attributed to the

Table 4

Summary of ductility exhibited by the HPDC processed secondary alloy having different casting thickness with respect to their corresponding microstructure analysis.

Thickness of sample (mm)	TE (%)	Presence of α -Fe intermetallics	Volume fraction of pores (%)	Presence of skin	Fracture driven by
2	1.5	Present	0.1	Present	Skin
6	2.9	Present	0.1	Absent	Cold flake
10	3.6	Present	0.8	Absent	Pores

die filling pattern through a crude explanation in Section 4.1 which, under actual physical conditions, could be even more complicated. Such complex flow of molten metal during the die filling stage can feasibly be influenced by the die geometry, temperature of the melt, plunger velocity, ingate velocity, ingate dimensions, etc. Thus, adjusting these process parameters may steer the ultimate mechanical response of the HPDC castings. At the same time, it should also be considered that the effects of tuning these casting parameters may even be more sensitive in case of the recycled secondary alloy given its novelty with respect to the chemical composition and physical properties. Thus, further research is needed for improved casting parameters or finding more suitable alloy.

5. Conclusions

In the current research, the evolution and effect of microstructure and casting defects on the ductility and fracture behavior (at a strain rate of 0.001 s^{-1}) of an HPDC processed recycled secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy with casting thickness between 2- and 10-mm have been analyzed. In addition, the effect of strain rate ($0.001, 0.1$ and 10 s^{-1}) on the tensile properties and fracture behavior demonstrated by the 2 mm thick HPDC casting has been investigated. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- (i) The HPDC process imparted fine-grained skin layer only on the surface of 2- (width of skin = 30–150 μm) and 4-mm (width of skin = 20–90 μm) thick castings and not in the 6- and 10-mm thick ones. Moreover, this layer was significantly discontinuous, meaning that it was not formed throughout on the casting surfaces.
- (ii) The absence as well as the inhomogeneous nature of the surface skin was attributed to the complex melt flow pattern inside the die cavity which results in varied heat transfer and cooling rate. The inhomogeneous skin layer acted as a crack initiation site owing to its weak bonding with the adjacent matrix, subsequently leading to abrupt fracture.
- (iii) When tested with different strain rates, on one hand, the overall flow strength of the HPDC processed secondary alloy arguably increased with increase in the strain rate. On the other hand, there was no relation between the ductility exhibited by the material and the strain rate.
- (iv) The large variation in ductility (between 1.6 and 6.8 %) demonstrated by the secondary alloy at varied strain rates could be correlated to the skin formation in the HPDC castings. When the castings possessed no skin or a continuous skin on its surface, it could withstand larger TE. Whereas if it contained an inhomogeneous skin on the surface, the material failed abruptly at different lower elongations.
- (v) The negative effect of the cold flake was insignificant when its weak flat surface boundary was nearly parallel to the loading direction. Whereas it became detrimental when the boundary was oriented at approximately 30° from the loading direction.
- (vi) The abundance of pores in the 10 mm thick casting restricted its ductility to 3.6 %. However, even though the 2- and 6-mm thick castings contained lower amount of pores, their ductility was even more restricted (to 1.5 and 2.9 %, respectively) because of the abrupt fracture triggered respectively by inhomogeneous skin and cold flake.
- (vii) The microstructural features were ranked according to their effect on the ductility exhibited by the HPDC processed secondary alloy, which follows a sequence of inhomogeneous skin, cold flakes and pores, with the inhomogeneity in skin formation turning out to be the most harmful one.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Biswajit Dalai: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft,

Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Simon Jonsson**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Manel da Silva**: Writing – review & editing, Resources, Formal analysis. **Fredrik Forsberg**: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Liang Yu**: Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jörgen Kajberg**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program under grant agreement No. 101069674 – Flexcrash project. The authors would like to thank Raff-metal for providing the material used in the current research and Eurecat for producing the high pressure die cast parts for experimental investigation. They are also grateful to the Division of Solid Mechanics, Division of Materials Science, Division of Fluid and Experimental Mechanics and Division of Chemical Engineering at Luleå University of Technology in Sweden for allowing to use their laboratories and equipment for carrying out the necessary experiments. Finally, the authors would like to extend their heartfelt gratitude to Dr. Vladimir Esin, University of Lorraine, France, for his helpful suggestions on the material characterization and manuscript preparation.

Data availability

The raw and processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

References

- J.G. Kaufman, E.L. Rooy, Aluminum casting alloys, in: *Alum. Alloy Cast. Prop. Process. Appl.*, ASM Int. (2004) 7–20. <http://saemuhendislik.com/alu2.pdf>.
- T.O. Mbuya, B.O. Odera, S.P. Ng'ang'a, Influence of iron on castability and properties of aluminium silicon alloys: literature review, *Int. J. Cast Met. Res.* 16 (2003) 451–465, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13640461.2003.11819622>.
- L. Wang, M. Makhlof, D. Apelian, Aluminium die casting alloys: alloy composition, microstructure, and properties-performance relationships, *Int. Mater. Rev.* 40 (1995) 221–238, <https://doi.org/10.1179/imr.1995.40.6.221>.
- L. Zhang, J. Gao, L.N.W. Damoah, D.G. Robertson, Removal of iron from aluminum: a review, *Miner. Process. Extr. Metall. Rev.* 33 (2012) 99–157, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08827508.2010.542211>.
- P. Crepeau, Effect of iron in Al-Si alloys: a critical review, *Trans. Am. Foundryman's Soc.* 103 (1995) 361–366.
- D. Apelian, Aluminum Cast Alloys: Enabling Tools for Improved Performance, in: *World Wide Rep, North American Die Casting Association*, Wheeling, Illinois, 2009. https://aluminium-guide.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/WWWR_AluminumCastAlloys.pdf.
- J.A. Taylor, Iron-containing intermetallic phases in Al-Si based casting alloys, *Procedia, Mater. Sci.* 1 (2012) 19–33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mspro.2012.06.004>.
- S.A.V.S. P. A. Società Alluminio Veneto, Aluminium alloys ingots for remelting: Alloy data sheet. <https://www.sav-al.com/file?oid=613f1e4c10834b044515e1f3>, 2020 (accessed July 26, 2024).
- L.A. Narayanan, F.H. Samuel, J.E. Gruzleski, Crystallization behavior of iron-containing intermetallic compounds in 319 aluminum alloy, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* 25 (1994) 1761–1773, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02668540>.
- M. da Silva, J. Pujante, J. Hrabia-Wisnioń, B. Augustyn, D. Kapinos, M. Węgrzyn, S. Boczek, Analysis of inclusions and impurities present in typical HPDC, stamping and extrusion alloys produced with different scrap levels, *Metals (Basel)*. 14 (2024) 626, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met14060626>.
- D. Bösch, S. Pogatscher, M. Hummel, W. Wagner, P.J. Uggowitzer, M. Göken, H. W. Höppel, Secondary Al-Si-mg high-pressure die casting alloys with enhanced ductility, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A* 46 (2015) 1035–1045, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-014-2700-8>.
- R. Lumley, The development of high strength and ductility in high-pressure die-cast Al-Si-mg alloys from secondary sources, *JOM* 71 (2019) 382–390, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-018-3121-8>.
- E. Cinkilic, M. Moodispaw, J. Zhang, J. Miao, A.A. Luo, A new recycled Al-Si-mg alloy for sustainable structural die casting applications, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* 53 (2022) 2861–2873, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-022-06711-4>.
- A. Niklas, A. Baquedano, S. Orden, E. Nogués, M. Da Silva, A.I. Fernández-Calvo, Microstructure and mechanical properties of a new secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy for ductile high pressure die casting parts for the automotive industry, *Key Eng. Mater.* 710 (2016) 244–249, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/KEM.710.244>.
- J.M. Sanchez, M. Arribas, H. Galarraga, M. Garcia de Cortazar, M. Ellero, F. Giro, Effects of Mn addition, cooling rate and holding temperature on the modification and purification of iron-rich compounds in AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy, *Heliyon* 9 (2023) e13005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13005>.
- J. Piątkowski, M. Hejne, R. Wieszała, Influence of manganese content on the microstructure and properties of AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy for die castings, *Arch. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 123 (2023) 5–12, <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0053.9750>.
- E. Cinkilic, C.D. Ridgeway, X. Yan, A.A. Luo, A formation map of iron-containing intermetallic phases in recycled cast aluminum alloys, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* 50 (2019) 5945–5956, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-019-05469-6>.
- A. Bakedano, R. González-Martínez, A. Niklas, M. Da Silva, M. Garat, A. I. Fernández-Calvo, Microstructural features of primary and secondary ductile high pressure die casting alloys for the automotive industry, in: *71st World Foundry Congr. Adv. Sustain. Foundry, WFC, 2014*, p. 2014.
- B. Dalai, S. Jonsson, M. da Silva, L. Yu, J. Kajberg, Inhomogeneous skin formation and its effect on the tensile behavior of a high pressure die cast recycled secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) alloy, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-024-07631-1>.
- H. Zheng, Y. Jiang, F. Liu, H. Zhao, Microstructure heterogeneity optimization of HPDC Al-Si-Mg-Cu alloys by modifying the characteristic of externally solidified crystals, *J. Alloys Compd.* 976 (2024) 173167, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2023.173167>.
- Z. Yuan, Z. Guo, S.M. Xiong, Skin layer of A380 aluminium alloy die castings and its blistering during solution treatment, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 35 (2019) 1906–1916, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2019.05.011>.
- H.M. Yang, Z. Guo, S.M. Xiong, Microstructure and mechanical properties of high-pressure die cast pure copper, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 275 (2020) 116377, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2019.116377>.
- S. Otarawanna, C.M. Gourlay, H.I. Laukli, A.K. Dahle, Formation of the surface layer in hypoeutectic Al-alloy high-pressure die castings, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 130 (2011) 251–258, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2011.06.035>.
- A. Niklas, A. Bakedano, S. Orden, M. da Silva, E. Nogués, A.I. Fernández-Calvo, Effect of microstructure and casting defects on the mechanical properties of secondary AlSi10MnMg(Fe) test parts manufactured by vacuum assisted high pressure die casting technology, *Mater. Today Proc.* 2 (2015) 4931–4938, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2015.10.059>.
- Y. Yang, S. Huang, J. Zheng, L. Yang, X. Cheng, R. Chen, H. Wei-jian, Effect of porosity and α -Al(Fe/Mn)Si phase on ductility of high-pressure die-casting Al–7Si–0.2Mg alloy, *Trans. Nonferrous Metals Soc. China* 34 (2024) 378–391, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326\(23\)66405-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326(23)66405-2).
- X.Y. Jiao, P.Y. Wang, Y.X. Liu, J. Wang, W.N. Liu, A.X. Wan, L.J. Shi, C.G. Wang, S. M. Xiong, Fracture behavior of a high pressure die casting AlSi10MnMg alloy with varied porosity levels, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 25 (2023) 1129–1140, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2023.05.281>.
- R. Liu, J. Zheng, L. Godlewski, J. Zindel, M. Li, W. Li, S. Huang, Influence of pore characteristics and eutectic particles on the tensile properties of Al-Si-Mn-Mg high pressure die casting alloy, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 783 (2020) 139280, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2020.139280>.
- Y. Zhang, E. Lordan, K. Dou, S. Wang, Z. Fan, Influence of porosity characteristics on the variability in mechanical properties of high pressure die casting (HPDC) AlSi7MgMn alloys, *J. Manuf. Process.* 56 (2020) 500–509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2020.04.071>.
- A. Niklas, S. Orden, A. Bakedano, M. da Silva, E. Nogués, A.I. Fernández-Calvo, Effect of solution heat treatment on gas porosity and mechanical properties in a die cast step test part manufactured with a new AlSi10MnMg(Fe) secondary alloy, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 667 (2016) 376–382, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2016.05.024>.
- X. Dong, X. Zhu, S. Ji, Effect of super vacuum assisted high pressure die casting on the repeatability of mechanical properties of Al-Si-Mg-Mn die-cast alloys, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 266 (2019) 105–113, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2018.10.030>.
- K. Dou, E. Lordan, Y. Zhang, A. Jacot, Z. Fan, A novel approach to optimize mechanical properties for aluminium alloy in high pressure die casting (HPDC) process combining experiment and modelling, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 296 (2021) 117193, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2021.117193>.
- B. Dybowski, A. Kielbus, Ł. Poloczek, Effects of die-casting defects on the blister formation in high-pressure die-casting aluminum structural components, *Eng. Fail. Anal.* 150 (2023) 107223, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfailanal.2023.107223>.
- W. Yu, H. Zhan, C.M. Gourlay, Effects of shot sleeve pre-solidification on the microstructure and tensile properties of high pressure die cast AE44, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* 55 (2024) 2019–2033, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-024-07376-x>.
- A.K.M.A. Ahamed, H. Kato, Influence of casting defects on tensile properties of ADC12 aluminum alloy die-castings, *Mater. Trans.* 49 (2008) 1621–1628, <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.F-MRA2008814>.

- [35] X.Y. Jiao, C.F. Liu, Z.P. Guo, G.D. Tong, S.L. Ma, Y. Bi, Y.F. Zhang, S.M. Xiong, The characterization of Fe-rich phases in a high-pressure die cast hypoeutectic aluminum-silicon alloy, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 51 (2020) 54–62, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2020.02.040>.
- [36] F. Liu, H. Zhao, R. Yang, F. Sun, Microstructure and mechanical properties of high vacuum die-cast AlSiMgMn alloys at as-cast and T6-treated conditions, *Materials (Basel)*. 12 (2019) 2065, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12132065>.
- [37] G. Ubertalli, F. D'Aiuto, S. Plano, D. De Caro, High strain rate behavior of aluminum die cast components, *Procedia Struct. Integr.* 2 (2016) 3617–3624, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2016.06.451>.
- [38] Trimet-05 data sheet, Trimal®-05: Die cast alloy for crash-relevant applications. <https://www.trimet.eu/en/products/foundry-alloys/trimal-05>, 2008. (Accessed 26 July 2024).
- [39] C.M. Dinnis, J.A. Taylor, A.K. Dahle, As-cast morphology of iron-intermetallics in Al-Si foundry alloys, *Scr. Mater.* 53 (2005) 955–958, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2005.06.028>.
- [40] X.Y. Jiao, Y.X. Liu, J. Wang, W.N. Liu, A.X. Wan, S. Wiesner, S.M. Xiong, The microstructure characteristics and fracture behavior of the polyhedral primary iron-rich phase and plate-shaped eutectic iron-rich phase in a high-pressure die-cast AlSi10MnMg alloy, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 140 (2023) 201–209, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2022.09.014>.
- [41] G. Gustafsson, T. Thorvaldsson, G.L. Dunlop, The influence of Fe and Cr on the microstructure of cast Al-Si-Mg alloys, *Metall. Trans. A.* 17 (1986) 45–52, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02644441>.
- [42] L. Lu, A.K. Dahle, Iron-rich intermetallic phases and their role in casting defect formation in hypoeutectic Al-Si alloys, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* 36 (2005) 819–835, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-005-1012-4>.
- [43] H. Kato, T. Suzuki, Y. Annou, K. Kageyama, Nondestructive detection of cold flakes in aluminum alloy die-cast plate with ultrasonic measurement, *Mater. Trans.* 45 (2004) 2403–2409, <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.45.2403>.
- [44] Z.W. Chen, Skin solidification during high pressure die casting of Al-11Si-2Cu-1Fe alloy, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 348 (2003) 145–153, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-5093\(02\)00747-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-5093(02)00747-5).
- [45] S. Midson, Die Casting Defects, n.d. <https://pdfcoffee.com/nadca-overview-of-defects-in-die-casting-pdf-free.html>.